

ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING SMALL-SCALE POULTRY FARMERS' ACCESS TO LOANS IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined small-scale poultry farmers' access to loans for poultry production in North Central Nigeria. Primary data were collected using questionnaires from the small-scale poultry farmers in the study area, while a random sampling technique was used to select 600 small-scale poultry farmers. Descriptive statistics (percentages and frequencies) and logistic regression were employed to achieve the study's objectives. Most (63.8%) of the respondents were male, and most (75%) were married. About 65.3% of the farmers had post-secondary education, while only 42.8% of them were members of cooperative societies. The average age of the farmers was 43 years, the mean household size was 6, and the average years of experience in poultry farming was 8 years. The average amount of interest paid by farmers on loans was N30,380.68 while the average loan repayment period was 3 months. The major constraint faced by the farmers in accessing loans in the study area was inadequate information on sources of loans. The study concluded that agricultural financing plays a critical role in improving poultry production. Hence, the study recommended that small-scale poultry farmers in north-central Nigeria should be sensitised on sources of loans available for poultry production by Agricultural extension agents.

Keywords: Small scale, Poultry farmers, Loan

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Poultry farming is vital in the global agricultural economy, contributing significantly to food security, employment generation, and economic development. Worldwide, the poultry industry has experienced rapid growth due to increasing demand for affordable protein sources such as eggs and poultry meat. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2020), poultry accounts for nearly 40% of the total meat production globally. However, the sector faces financial constraints despite its potential, particularly for small-scale poultry farmers who often lack access to affordable credit.

Inadequate access to loans restricts their ability to expand operations, adopt modern technologies, and meet growing consumer demand.

In Nigeria, the poultry industry is one of the most significant segments of the agricultural sector, contributing about 25% of the total livestock output and supporting millions of livelihoods (Erdaw and Beyene, 2022). North Central Nigeria, with its favourable climatic conditions and vast arable land, is a prominent hub for poultry production. However, small-scale poultry farmers in the region face significant challenges in accessing credit facilities. Despite various government initiatives,

such as the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and intervention programs like the Anchor Borrowers Program, many farmers struggle to meet the eligibility criteria for loans. Factors such as lack of collateral, high transaction costs, and limited awareness of available loan schemes further exacerbate the problem.

The loan is both an input used in production and a facilitator of the efficiency of other production inputs. An agricultural loan refers to the amount of investment fund which is provided for agricultural production from sources independent of the farm sector. The availability of loans for agricultural purposes is mostly seen as very efficient in enhancing the productivity of farmers (Ahamefule *et al.*, 2017). Also, it is believed that if agricultural credit is made available and accessible to poultry production and other agricultural activities, the production and supply of poultry products in Nigeria will improve. Some of the factors which will determine poultry farmers' access to credit include the size of the poultry, location of the farm, access to extension services, socio-economic characteristics like level of education and others. One of the fastest ways to boost agricultural production is the introduction of easy and cheap credit (Ahamefule *et al.*, 2017).

Understanding the factors that influence small-scale poultry farmers' access to loans and the challenges they face is crucial for developing targeted interventions to support their needs. By addressing these challenges, policymakers, agricultural extension workers, and financial institutions can help improve small-scale poultry farmers' access to finance, ultimately enhancing their livelihoods and contributing to the

development of the poultry sector in North Central Nigeria.

The broad objective of the study is to analyze the small-scale poultry farmers' access to loans for poultry production in North Central Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of small-scale poultry farmers in the study area.
- ii. determine the average interest paid and repayment period for loans obtained by small-scale poultry farmers in the study area.
- iii. analyze the relationship between farmers' socio-economic characteristics and access to loans.
- iv. investigate the constraints to accessing loans by small-scale poultry farmers in the study area.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in the North Central Nigeria (Figure 3.1). This is one of the six geo-political zones in the country and is made up of 7 states which include: Kwara, Kogi, Niger, Nasarawa, Benue, and Plateau States, as well as Abuja. The study area is located between latitude 10° 20' 00" N and longitude 7° 45' 00" E. The largest state in the zone is Niger State, with a land mass of 76,363 square kilometres, while the smallest state in the zone, with a land mass of 27,117 square kilometres, is Benue State. The languages common in the areas include Nupes, Idomas, Tivs, Igalas, Idomas, Gwaris, Bassa, Gedegede, Yorubas, Ibiras and many others (Olayemi, 2014). Poultry production is a vital aspect of agriculture in North Central Nigeria, contributing significantly to the livelihoods, food security, and income of rural and urban households. Local/Indigenous Breeds include the

Fulani chicken and kuroila birds, while the exotic breeds include broilers, layers and cockerel.

2.2 Sampling Technique

A simple random sampling technique was used to sample respondents for the study from five states in North-central Nigeria. A sample frame showing the number of poultry farmers was collected from the states. From each of the states, 120 small-scale poultry farmers were randomly selected, totaling 600 respondents. An equal number of respondents was sampled from each of the states and Abuja to avoid bias that may be introduced due to unequal data.

2.3 Data Collection and analysis

Primary data were used for the study and were collected with the aid of well-structured questionnaire which were administered to poultry farmers in the study area by the researcher with the help of trained ADP enumerators from the states under study. This is because they have a good understanding of the community and their local language for effective data collection.

Objectives i, ii, iii, iv and viii; objective v was achieved using analysis of variance (ANOVA), objective vi was actualized using t-test, while objective vii was achieved using logistics regression.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to their gender. Most (64%) of the respondents were males while only 36% of them were females. Traditionally, agriculture, including poultry farming, has been perceived as a male-dominated sector (Haimid, Masdek, Rahim and Rahim, 2016). The result also revealed that most (75%) of the farmers were married. About 13% of them were single, 8% were widowed while remaining 4% were divorced. On the educational qualifications of respondents as displayed

in Table 4.1, about 65.3% of the respondents had post-secondary school education. About 27% of them had secondary school education, 3.8% had primary education while the remaining 3.8% had no formal education. The result further shows that most (57%) of the poultry farmers were not members of any cooperative societies, while 42.8% were members of one cooperative society or the other. Higher membership strengthens the collective bargaining power of the association. This enables farmers to negotiate better deals for the purchase of inputs, equipment, and services, leading to potential cost savings (Onyeneke Emenekwe, Chidiebere-Mark, Munonye, Aligbe, Kanu and Azuamairo, 2020).

The respondents' age, as displayed in Table 1, indicates that the majority (56.3%) of the respondents were between the ages of 31 and 40 years, while those who were between 21 and 30 years old accounted for 40.7% of the respondents. About 1.7% of them were between the ages of 41 and 50, while those who were 51 years of age or older and those who were at most 20 years of age accounted for 1.1% and 0.2%, respectively. The average age of the farmers was 43 years and 6 months.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the farmers by household size reveals that most (53%) of them had a household size of 6-10 people, 38.8% had a household size of not more than 5 people while 4.5% of them had a family size of 11-15 people. The result further shows that only 3.3% of the farmers had a household size of more than 15 people. The average household size of the respondents was 6. A larger household may be able to allocate resources more efficiently. Still, in Table 1, the distribution of the farmers by their farming experience shows that most (76%) of them had been involved in poultry production for not more than 10 years. About 20% had between 11 and 20 years of experience in poultry farming, while only

3.6% had been involved in poultry production for more than 20 years. Meanwhile, the mean farming experience of the respondents was 8 years. Farmers with experience are better equipped to assess and manage risks associated with

agriculture, such as disease outbreaks, pests, and market fluctuations. Their ability to anticipate and respond to challenges helps in minimizing potential losses (Akintunde, Coster, Nwigwe and Agboola, 2020).

Table 1: Respondents' Socio-economic Characteristics

Socio-economic Characteristics	Frequency	Percent	Mean
Gender			
Male	381	63.8	
Female	216	36.2	
Marital Status			
Single	78	13.1	
Married	447	75.0	
Divorced	21	3.5	
Widow	50	8.4	
Level of Education			
No School at all	23	3.8	
I completed Primary School	23	3.8	
I completed Secondary School	162	27.0	
I have HSC/OND/NCE certificate	183	30.5	
I have B.Sc/HND degree	192	32.0	
I have M.Sc	14	2.3	
I have PhD	3	0.5	
Membership of Cooperative Society			
Yes	257	42.8	
No	343	57.2	
Age			
= 20	1	0.2	43.5
21 – 30	244	40.7	
31 – 40	338	56.3	
41 – 50	10	1.7	
= 51	7	1.1	
Household Size			
= 5	233	38.8	6
6 – 10	320	53.3	
11 – 15	27	4.5	
= 16	20	3.3	
Years of Poultry Farming Experience			
= 10	457	76.2	8
11 – 20	121	20.2	
21 – 30	11	1.8	
= 31	11	1.8	
Total	600	100.0	

Average interest paid and average duration of the loan

The result for the average interest paid and the average loan tenure available to farmers is presented in Table 2. The result shows that the highest amount of interest paid by the farmers is N800,000 while the least amount paid for interest was N5,000. However, the average interest paid by farmers on loans was N30,380.68. For the loan tenure, the study revealed that the longest duration for loan repayment was 36 months while the least was 1 month. The average loan repayment period was 3 months. According to Akintunde *et al.* (2020), one of the major determinants of

loan access among the farmers is interest rates. Interest rates can significantly impact farmers' access to loans. Higher interest rates increase the cost of borrowing, making loans less affordable for farmers. This can limit their ability to invest in equipment, seeds, and other resources, affecting productivity. Lower interest rates, on the other hand, make loans more accessible and can stimulate agricultural development by facilitating investment in technology and sustainable practices (Owusu-Antwi and Antwi, 2010). Economic policies and lending institutions play crucial roles in shaping these dynamics.

Table 2: Average interest paid and average duration of the loan

Average Interest Paid and Duration	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Average Interest Paid (₦)	30,380.68	5,000	800,000
Average Duration (Months) of Loan	3	1	36

Socio-Economic Factors that Influence Access to Loans by Poultry Farmers

Table 3 shows the result of the logistic regression analysis on the effect of socio-economic factors on access to loans by poultry farmers in the study area. The Nagelkerke R^2 is a measure of how well the independent variables in the model explain the variation in the dependent variable. In this case, the value of 0.41 indicates that approximately 41% of the variations in access to loans by poultry farmers can be predicted by the socio-economic factors included in the model. This is a moderately strong explanatory power, suggesting that the model captures a significant portion of the variability in loan access. The remaining 59% of the variations not explained by the model could be attributed to unobserved variables, measurement errors, or other factors that were not

included in the analysis. The shows that age, farming experience, and membership in cooperatives were the significant variables influencing access to loans by the farmers. The term significant in this context means that changes in these variables were associated with a statistically significant impact on the likelihood of poultry farmers having access to loans or not.

The regression result (Table 3) reveals that age (0.029) was negative and significant at 5% probability. This implies that age has an inverse relationship with access to loans. Hence, for a unit increase in age, if every other variable is constant, there is a likelihood that access to loans by poultry farmers in the study area will decrease. Older borrowers may be perceived as higher risk by lenders and may have less stable income sources, particularly if they are retired or approaching retirement

(Lusardi, Mitchell and Oggero, 2020). This may lead to reluctance on the part of financial institutions to offer them loans. Also, lenders might be concerned about the repayment capacity of older borrowers due to a potentially shorter time horizon.

Farming experience (0.027) was positive and significant at 5% probability. Hence, an increase in farming experience, if every other variable is constant, will likely lead to an increase in access to loans by poultry farmers in the study area. Experience in farming might influence access to loans, possibly because experienced farmers are often perceived as more credible and trustworthy by lenders (Chowa, Garforth and Cardey, 2013). Their long history in farming demonstrates a commitment to the industry and an ability to manage agricultural activities over time. This credibility reduces the perceived risk for lenders. Also, farmers with extensive experience are likely to have a better understanding of financial management

and the economic aspects of farming. They are more adept at planning, budgeting, and managing loans effectively. This financial literacy increases their chances of successfully applying for and utilizing loans.

Also, the result revealed that membership of cooperative society is positive and significant at 5% probability level (Table 3). This implies that membership of cooperatives has a positive relationship with access to loan. Membership of cooperatives increases the chances of accessing loans. Cooperatives pool the resources and interests of many members, providing greater leverage to negotiate favorable loan terms with financial institutions (Spielman, Cohen and Mogues, 2008). This means that banks and lending institutions are more likely to offer better interest rates and terms to cooperatives due to their collective risk-sharing.

Table 3: Result of Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-Economic Factors Affecting Poultry Farmers' Access to Loans

Variable	B	Std. Error	Wald	
Gender	.123	.186	.436	.509
Marital Status	.021	.111	.035	.852
HHS	.036	.038	.879	.348
Age	-.023	.011	4.738	*.029
Farming Experience	.048	.022	4.879	*.027
Education Level	.097	.078	1.550	.213
Cooperative	.404	.168	5.821	*.016
Constant	-.560	.634	.781	.377

Cox and Snell R squared = 0.41

*significant at 5% probability

Constraints Faced by small-scale Poultry Farmers in Accessing Loan

Table 4 shows the poultry farmers' response to the challenges limiting their access to loans in the study area. The result showed that inadequate information on sources of loans was the biggest challenge faced by the farmers, as shown by 44% of the responses. This agrees with the assertions of Wangechi and Waweru (2015), which affirm that access to information plays an important role in improving access to loans. Inadequate loan information for farmers can lead to financial instability and hinder sustainable agriculture. Farmers may struggle to make informed decisions, resulting in improper budgeting, misallocation of resources, and difficulty in repaying loans. This lack of

transparency can perpetuate a cycle of debt, affecting farmers' overall productivity and livelihoods. Additionally, insufficient information may limit access to better financial opportunities, hindering agricultural development and exacerbating poverty in rural communities. Also, the short duration for loan repayment was another major constraint faced by the farmers in accessing loans, as shown by 43.5%, while 37.3% of the respondents indicated the long process and bureaucracies as one of the major challenges they faced in accessing loans. Other constraints faced by the farmers include a lack of collaterals (18.7%), high interest rates charged on loans (10%) and a lack of confidence in the farmers by creditors or financial institutions.

Table 4: Challenges limiting small-scale Poultry Farmers ' Access to Loan

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of collaterals	112	18.7
Long process involved in processing loan	224	37.3
Lack of confidence in me by the source	36	6.0
Inadequate information on sources of loan	267	44.5
High interest rate charged on the loan	60	10.0
Short duration for loan repayment	261	43.5

Note: Multiple responses allowed

CONCLUSION

The analysis of small-scale poultry farmers' access to loans in North Central Nigeria revealed the critical role financing plays in sustaining poultry production. The challenges identified, including inadequate information and limited access to credit, underscore the need for targeted interventions to empower poultry farmers. Addressing these issues through improved financial literacy, streamlined loan application processes, and fostering collaboration between financial institutions and poultry farmers will enhance access to credit and contribute to the overall growth and sustainability of small-scale poultry farming in the study area. As we navigate the complexities of agricultural finance, it becomes evident that fostering a supportive environment is paramount for the prosperity of small-scale

poultry farmers and the broader agricultural landscape. Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Poultry production policy formulations and implementation should involve continuous consultation among stakeholders, such as producers, input suppliers, and extension agents. This will lead to more effective policies regarding small-scale poultry access to loans.
 - ii. The Government of Nigeria and other stakeholders should address the problem of high interest rates on loans for poultry production, as this will encourage farmers to access the loans and increase production.
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